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MAGNETIC PROPERTIES OF SOFT MAGNETIC COMPOSITES USED IN ELECTROMECHANICAL ENGINEERING

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Abstract

The article discusses the methods of using composite magnetic alloys for elements of electrical engineering. The main methods of obtaining soft magnetic composite materials have been studied in order to obtain high-performance MMC particles, as it should be subjected to electrically insulated powder to obtain high-density parts. High densities generally improve magnetic properties, both to keep hysteresis losses low and to obtain high flux density. These give an effect when used for the cores of electric motors based on magnetically soft composite materials.

Keywords: composite, soft magnetic, materials, cores, rotors and stators, hysteresis curve, magnetic alloys, mechanical and magnetic density of alloys, ponder motive force.

Introduction. It is known that of all metals, only three metals, for example, iron, nickel, cobalt, have ferromagnetism, i.e. the ability to significantly thicken magnetic field lines, which is characterized by magnetic permeability. The relative magnetic permeability of ferromagnetic metals reaches tens and hundreds of thousands of units; for the rest, it is close to unity, if the relative permeability is somewhat greater than unity, then it is paramagnetic, and if it is less than unity, it is diamagnetic [1,3].

The purpose of this work is to develop the main elements of electrical machines using composite magnetically soft materials.

Soft magnetic materials are used for applications such as core materials in inductors, stators and rotors for electrical machines, drives, sensors and transformer cores. Traditionally, soft magnetic cores, such as rotors and stators in electrical machines, are made from stacked steel lamellar magnetic cores. Soft magnetic composite (SMC) materials are based on soft magnetic particles, usually based on iron, with an electrically insulating coating on each particle [2 - 4]. By pressing the isolated particles, optionally together with lubricants and/or binders, using a conventional powder metallurgy process, MMC parts are obtained. By using this powder metallurgical technology, it is possible to obtain MMC components with a higher degree of freedom in design than using steel lamellar magnetic cores, since the MMC material can carry three-dimensional magnetic flux, and also because three-dimensional shapes can be obtained as a result of the pressing process. In order to make MMC parts highly efficient and

reduce their size, it is necessary to improve the operational characteristics of soft magnetic powders [4, 5].

Methods. One important parameter for improving the performance of MMC parts is to reduce their core loss characteristics. When a magnetic material is subjected to an alternating field, energy losses occur due to both hysteresis losses and eddy current losses. The hysteresis loss is proportional to the frequency of the alternating magnetic fields, while the eddy current loss is proportional to the square of the frequency. Thus, at high frequencies, it is predominantly eddy current losses that matter, and there is a particular need to reduce eddy current losses and at the same time keep hysteresis losses low. This means that it is desirable to increase the electrical resistivity of magnetic cores [6].

Results and Discussion. The experimental density was determined by the hydrostatic weighing method [3, 4], which is as follows. First, the sample is weighed in air at room temperature, and then the sample is immersed in distilled water [6, 7]. Samples in the form of compressed cores were taken for weighing. The experimental density d_{exp} is determined from the expression:

$$d_{exp} = \frac{P_1 \cdot d_T - P_1 \cdot d_{air}}{P_1 - P_2} \quad (1)$$

where:

P_1 - is the weight of the sample in air;

P_2 is the weight of the sample immersed in distilled water;

d_T is the density of distilled water at a given temperature;

d_{air} is the air density.

The accuracy of this method is determined by the accuracy of determining its weight and the density of the liquid used.

In addition, in order to further reduce the hysteresis loss, stress relief heat treatment of the pressed part is required. In order to achieve effective stress relief, the heat treatment should preferably be carried out at a temperature above 300°C and below the temperature at which the insulating coating would be damaged, i.e. about 600°C, in a non-reducing atmosphere [7].

When studying the magnetic properties of the samples, a setup was used, which is based on the method of measuring the ponder motive force. The method makes it possible to study the temperature dependences of the magnetization and magnetic susceptibility at small amounts of matter [2, 6]. This makes it possible to relatively quickly achieve temperature equilibrium over the entire volume of the sample. It is obvious that the absence of a temperature gradient on the sample at the moment of measuring the specific magnetization or susceptibility provides the most accurate determination of their values.

As is known [3], the ponder motive force is determined by the expression:

$$F = m\sigma_x \frac{\partial B}{\partial x} = \frac{m\chi_g}{\mu_0} B \frac{\partial B}{\partial x} \quad (2)$$

where m is the mass of the sample, σ_x , χ_g are the magnetization and magnetic susceptibility of the unit mass of the sample, respectively, μ_0 is the magnetic constant, B is the magnetic induction, $\partial B/\partial x$ - is the magnetic induction gradient B along the x axis.

Measurements of the values of magnetic characteristics carried out by this method can be carried out with an accuracy of 1% if a calibration sample of the same shape and size is available (for example, from nickel) [5, 6].

The choice of electromagnet parameters is determined by the maximum values of the sample dimensions. The electromagnet must create a magnetic field

that has a constant value of the product of the strength H and its gradient $\partial H/\partial x$ in a space of such dimensions between the pole pieces that it overlaps the dimensions of the ampoule in which the sample is located with a margin.

Figure 1 shows a schematic diagram of the installation. The electromagnet contains an annular magnetic circuit and cores with pole pieces made of E12 steel [3,4]. The electromagnet's design allows to add the 2Z space between them. The diameter of the pole pieces $d = 145$ mm. The electromagnet coils are wound with a 2 mm × 5 mm copper bar with the number of turns increasing towards the outer ends of the core. A similar method of variable winding is typically used in solenoids to increase field uniformity and eliminate the edge scattering effect. The annular magnetic circuit of the electromagnet, on the one hand, ensures the minimum scattering of the magnetic field in space. On the other hand, with a vertical arrangement, such a design is convenient for turning the electromagnet at any angle relative to a stationary sample [7, 8]. When used in order to prevent the sample from sticking to the pole pieces and at the same time ensure sufficient measurement accuracy, the mass of the sample, for example, of a ferromagnetic substance, should not exceed a few milligrams, and of an antiferromagnetic substance, of the order of one gram. To study the main magnetic characteristics of composite magnetic materials using ASC100.29 iron powders, 24 × 13 × 10 mm cores were made from materials with a density of $\rho = 7.6$ g/cm³ [9].

Samples of composite magnetic material were annealed in vacuum at a temperature of 350°C for 3 hours. The electromagnetic characteristics were studied using an F5050 microwebermeter. Measurement of the frequency characteristics of composite materials in a wide range of magnetic fields, magnetization reversal frequencies and temperatures was carried out on an express magnetometer in the frequency range up to 10 kHz and magnetic fields up to 30 kA/m [6, 7].

Figure 1. - Block diagram of the installation for magnetic 1 - electromagnet; 2 - device for reading the force of drawing the sample into the magnetic field; 3 - sample unit a thermostat; 4 - device for vacuuming the measurement thermostat

Before normalizing the magnetometer, the magnetic properties are measured on a fluxmeter.

In this case, an F5050 microwebermeter was used to normalize the magnetometer. Figure 2 shows the appearance of the magnetometer, and figure 3 shows the results of express magnetometer data processing and the main characteristics of its operation.

The magnetometer is designed for express control of the magnetic properties of materials - measurement in a wide frequency range of curves of magnetization reversal of samples, magnetic permeability and total losses, both during magnetization reversal and with one-sided magnetization. The set of express flux meter-magnetometer also includes software for processing measurement results [7,9].

Figure 2 - Appearance of the magnetometer

Conclusion. In order to obtain highly efficient MMC particles, it must also be possible to subject the electrically insulated powder to compression molding at high pressures, since this is very often desirable in order to obtain high density parts. High densities generally improve the magnetic properties. In particular,

high densities are needed to keep hysteresis losses low and to obtain high saturation flux density.

Additionally, the electrical insulation must withstand the required high compression pressures without being damaged when the pressed part is ejected from the mould.

Figure 3. Results of data processing in the express flux meter (a) and express magnetometer (b) modes

The results obtained during the study indicate the possibility of developing new magnetically soft composite materials and the prospects for their practical application for the creation of various electrical devices, the main element for the core elements of the rotors and stators of the electric motor.

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FORMATION OF A METHODOLOGICAL SYSTEM OF ASSIMILATION OF INFORMATION ABOUT TECHNOLOGICAL MACHINES, DEVICES, TOOLS AND MECHANISMS, THE PRINCIPLES OF THEIR OPERATION

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Abstract

The article focuses on the challenges of the “techno-Democratic-Information Society”, the “technology” subject curriculum taught at secondary schools, the expected results in the teaching of this subject, the information to be mastered to students as a component in terms of the realization of the expected results, the theoretical level of the above-mentioned information., the need to establish the regularities of the process of active-interactive training is argued. As a concrete manifestation of the process of forming a methodological system for mastering the principles of work of technological machines, devices, tools and mechanisms, two examples are presented, which include a table for an active-interactive organization.

Keywords: Technological machine, device, tool, mechanism, executive body, engine, transmission, transmission ratio, carrying and carrying pulleys, transmission number.

Relevance of the research topic. In the social, economic, and cultural life of our country, a comprehensive reform program is being implemented that is adequate to the challenges of our time. One of the objectives in choosing education as a priority direction of development in this process is the successful preparation of the emerging young generation for life from an early age. Based on logic, it can be argued that an integral element (an important link) of preparing the younger generation for life, for practical activity is the training of qualified specialists who meet the requirements of the pace of development of our country. This reality was in the center of attention in the “program of reforms in the field of education of the Republic of Azerbaijan”.

Information about technological machines, devices, tools and mechanisms, containing as a component the content of the expected results in the teaching of the subject “Technology”, mandatory for teaching in secondary schools, the principles of which are subordinated to the “immanent function”, is a “cognitive issue of didactic nature” of the formation of a methodological system aimed at its assimilation. This question relates to the problem of system formation, which is broader. This gap is eternal in connection with the development of a system that ensures the implementation of the expected results in the discipline “technology”. Therefore, we affirm the relevance of the topic formulated in the direction of the formation of a methodological system for the assimilation of information about technological machines, devices, tools and mechanisms, the principles of their operation.

Interpretation of materials obtained in the research process.

It is known that the formation of the educational space is based on the paradigm “man - society-

technology (which in the modern period of time becomes adequate to the calls for the IV Industrial Revolution)-nature”, which is a prerequisite for the free development of man or the path of development aimed at civilization. This idea, voiced by us in connection with the formation of the educational space, is not erroneous, since we come to the conclusion that education is a superstructure phenomenon, “education is not life itself, but only readiness for it”[5;203]. Naturally, the education of the present time, by its cognitive (cognitive) nature, can play an increasingly important role in the formation of a person as a person. [5;3]. Today, the successes achieved by Azerbaijan, which has successfully stepped on the path of independence, in the field of education, are formed as a result of a consistent and continuous educational policy. An integrative education system based on democratic, humanistic principles is already being formed in Azerbaijan. In the newly created education, the main factor is considered to be taking into account the parameters of cognitive development, creating its capabilities and conditions [5; 7].

For the first time in the history of education in our country, a curriculum document was developed at the national level in 2006. This document entitled “The Concept of General Secondary Education (National Curriculum) in the Republic of Azerbaijan” is distinguished by the fact that it can serve the formation of personality, the formation of life skills in it, taking into account national and universal values, general development, trends and interests, the creation of favorable learning conditions for all students, built on the principles of relevance, effectiveness and integrativity.[1] subject curricula based on the “concept of general secondary education in the Republic of Azerbaijan”, in particular, the curriculum “technology”